

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TIFUNTOH****FIRST NAME: CHRISTOPHER KONDE****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The Author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used Turabian/Chicago footnote (Zotero) and confirmed below:

The Author used Zotero to insert references

The Author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The Author used Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D COURSE

1. What is research within the context of ACA-401D?

- Ethical considerations, submissions, funding detailed methodology,
- A detailed outline of the study, methodology feasibility, identified problem, analysis
- A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others want to solve.¹**
- Topic, introduction, research questions, bibliography.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19, <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226430607.001.0001>.

2. **Indicate the list that best describes settling on a quality research topic.**
- Search the internet, search older topics, ask senior colleagues, and ask classmates.
 - Search your interests, make your topic manageable, question your topic, and evaluate your questions.²**
 - All of the above
 - None of the above
3. **How do you reference a single-authored book using the Turabian Author-Date citation style?**
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (parentheses), Title (quotation mark), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
 - Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
 - Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.³**
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
4. What are the main components of the initial parts of a dissertation? Indicate the correct sequence.

² Turabian et al., 23–28.

³ Turabian et al., 229.

- Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, and Abstract.**⁴
- Title, Prefects, Dedication, Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, belief, and Abstract.
- Title, Dedication, Supervisory Committee Page, Acknowledgments, List of Tables, Table of Contents, List of Figures, Abstract, and Biography.
- All of the above.
5. **How is a quotation written in line with UK English about quotation marks?**
- Quotation marks are used for both.
- The quotation starts with inverted commas; the quotation within this is in quotation marks.
- The quotation starts with quotation marks; the quotation within this is in inverted commas.**⁵
- Both parties use inverted commas.
6. **What is the typical structure or organization of a Ph.D. thesis?**

⁴ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 24–26.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University, 2024), 31.

- The initial parts, Chapter 1 – Introduction, Chapter 2 – Review of the Literature, Chapter 3 – Methods, Chapter 4 – Findings, and Chapter 5 – Discussion.⁶**
 - Chapter 1 – Introduction, Chapter 2 – Research question and methodology, Chapter 3 – Summary of results, chapter 4 – General discussion.
 - Initial parts, Chapter 1 – Introduction, Chapter 2 – Theoretical and Conceptual, Chapter 3 – Literature Review, Chapter 4 – Case Study Organization, Chapter 5 – Research Methodology, Chapter 6 – Presentation and Data Analysis, and Chapter 7 – Conclusion and Recommendations.
 - The initial parts, Chapter 1 – Introduction, Chapter 2 – Review of the Literature, Chapter 3 – Methodology, Chapter 4 – Findings, and Chapter 5 – Discussion.
7. **Tick the correct response below that indicates the appropriate scholarly method for a qualitative dissertation.**
- Focus groups, one-on-one interviews, case studies, qualitative observation, and ethnographic research.
 - Briefly describe the methods, equipment, procedures, the limitations encountered, sample collection, and data analysis.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 66–76.

- Research sample, research design, method of data collection, data collection methods, data analysis and synthesis, ethical consideration, trustworthiness issues, limitation, and delimitation.**⁷
- Design justification, design paraphrase, data collection and analysis, study design.
8. **What does gender-inclusive language mean when writing for an EU audience?**
- Gender-neutral and masculine pronouns refer to both men and women.
- Avoid word choices that may be interpreted as implying that one gender.**⁸
- Avoid focusing on gender issues; just present as you want to.
- All of the above.
9. **What is the appropriate date format for writing for the EU audience?**
- Day month year
- Day-Month-Year
- Day Month (spelt in full) Year.**⁹
- Month, Day, year.
10. **What is the difference between notes-bibliography and author-date styles in citation formats?**

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 439–80.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Commission, 2021), 63.

⁹ European Commission, 39.

- The notes-bibliography style uses in-text citations, while the author-date style uses footnotes.
- Both styles use footnotes for citation.
- The notes-bibliography style uses footnotes, while the author-date style uses in-text citations.¹⁰**
- Both styles use in-text citations for citation.

¹⁰ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 177–79.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University Of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.